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Human Excellence In The Abhijnanasakuntalam Of Kalidasa

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Introduction:-

Kalidasa himself was a bright example of human excellence. Otherwise he would not have been a Mahakavi, great poet. Who is a great poet? As per Anandavardhana¹, great poet are countable few. He said²- great poet is endowed with pratibha, poetic talent and are capable of utilizing suggestive meanings. As a figure of those to development, Kalidasa was a Mahakavi, great poet. That is why, Jayadev called him the guiding spirit of all classical sanskrit poets. In addition to metrical poems, he produced beautiful prose pieces. His three dramas are the evidence. In the Abhijnanasakuntalam³, he says: आर्य अभिरुपभूयिष्ठापरिषदियम् अद्यखलुकालिदासग्रथितवस्तुना नवेनाभिज्ञानशकुन्तलाख्येन नाटकेनोप-स्थातव्यमस्माभिः। तत् प्रतिपात्रमाधियतां यत्नः। Ready to go away to the house of her husband, Sakuntala escorted the pregnant deer, says⁴ तात एषोऽजपर्यन्तचारिणी गर्भमन्थरामृगवधूर्यदाऽनघप्रसवा भवतितदा मह्यं किमपि प्रियानिवेदयितुकं विसर्जयिष्यथा। With the determination of the speed of chariot, the king says⁵, (रथवेगं निरुपयन्) साधुसाधु। अनेनरथवेगेनपूर्वप्रस्थिनं वैनतेयमप्यासाधयेयं किंपुनस्तमपकारिणमघोनः~ At the very introduction of Malavikagnimitram, Pariparsvika and Sutradhara says⁶ - "अभिहितोऽस्मि विदूत्परिषदा-कालिदासग्रथितवस्तुमालविकाग्निमित्रनामनाटकमस्मिन्वसन्तोत्सवे प्रयोक्तव्यमिति। तदारभ्यतां संगीतकम्। पारिपार्श्विक :-मातावत्। प्रथितयशसां भाससौमिल्लककविपुत्रादिनां प्रबन्धानक्रिम्य वर्तमानकवेः कालिदासस्य क्रियायां कथवहुमानः। There are numerous dramas in the Sanskrit literature. But the Abhijnanasakuntalam of Kalidasa is unanimously head to be the greatest one. This ascertainment all talented Sanskrit scholar is highly vociferous of the human excellence of Kalidasa. There is a proverb⁷ -

काव्येसुनाटकं रम्यं तत्र रम्या शकुन्तला।

तत्रापि च चतुर्थोऽङ्क तत्रश्लोक चतुष्टयम्॥

Beautiful is the drama among the Sanskrit epic poems. The most beautiful among the dramas is Abhijnanasakuntalam the fourth act of the same are most important. Four verses of the fourth act are stupendous.

Sriharsa, the most talented Sanskrit scholar in poet, has spoken in the khandanakhandakhadyam⁸-

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अबिकल्पविषय एकः स्थाणुः पुरुषः श्रुतोऽस्ति यः श्रुतिषु ।
ईश्वरमुमया नपरं वन्देऽतुमयापि तमधिगतम् ॥ १ ॥

This verse wonderfully consider with the verse of Kalidasa. Kalidasa who was much earlier to him . In the opening verse of Vikramorvasiyamkalidasa says⁹ —

वेदान्तेषु यमाहुरेकपुरुषं व्याप्य स्थितंरोदसी ,
यस्मिन्नीश्वर इत्यनन्यविषयः शब्द यथार्थाक्षरः।
अन्तर्यश्च मुमुक्षुभिर्नियमितप्राणादिभिर्मुनय वः ,
श स्थाणुः स्थिरभक्तियोगसुलभो निःश्रेयसासास्तुवः॥

Naisadhiyacharitam says¹⁰ — that Sriharsa, the great poet, was a Sanskrit scholar extraordinary. He had wonderful access to eighteen branches¹¹ of knowledge. He held Kalidasa in great respect by imitating him in the verse already coated. From his imitation, It is clear that Kalidasa was a versatile scholar – a bright example of human excellence.

1.1 Personal Excellence In The Abhijnanasakuntalam Of Kalidasa.

The king Dusyanta was the very popular powerful king in the famous drama Abhijnanasakuntalam.

It is not wonderful that he whose arm is long as the bar of city gate alone protects the whole earth bounded by the dark green ocean. For the Gods rooted in their enmity with the demons, rely for victory in battles on his braced bow and Indra's thunder-bolt.

नैतचित्रं यदयमुदधिश्यामसीमां धरित्री-
मेकः कृत्सानगरपरिषपारंशुबाहुर्भुनक्ति।
आशंसक्ते सुरयुवतयो बुद्धवैराहि दैत्यै
रस्याधिज्येधनुषि विजयं पौरुहुते च वज्रेः॥

The king Dusyanta has an outstanding personal activity. The gatekeeper shown the power of Dusyatnta and says-

अनवरतधनुर्ज्यास्फालन क्रुरपूर्वम्
रविकिरणसहिष्णुस्वेदलेशेरभिन्नम्।
अपचितमपिगात्रं व्यायतत्वादलक्ष्यं
गिरिचरइवनागः प्राणसारंविभर्ति॥

Why talk of aiming the shaft? For by the mere sound of the bow-string from afar, as if by the angry murmur of his bow, he disperses our obstacle.

And smiling to see Jayanta, who stood near him, filled with an word longing a wreath of Mandara flowers

marked with the yellow- sandal from its rubbing on his breast, was by Indra placed about my neck-

मन्दारमालाहारिणपिनद्धा।

With the residue of colours used by nymphs of heaven to adorn their persons, this dwellers of heaven are writing your exploits on vestment of the heavenly trues thinking out verses suitable for singing.

विच्छित्तिशेषैः सुरसुन्दरिणांवरैरमिकल्पलतांशुकेषु।
विचिन्त्यगीतक्षममर्थजातं दिवौकसस्त्वञ्चारितंलिखन्ति॥

In Abhijnanasakuntalam king Dusyanta has better personality with human excellence when he doubt to sakuntala and says-

असंशय क्षत्रपरिग्रहक्षमा यदार्यमस्याभिलाषि मेमनः।
सतांहिसन्देहपदेषुवस्तुषुप्रमाणमन्तः करणप्रवृत्तयः॥

1.2 Social Excellence In Abhijnanasakuntalam

Social human excellence is very important for human being. Family, Ethics, behaviour are come under the social human excellence.

Abhijnanasakuntalam have been related with social human excellence, marriage life of Dusyanta and Sakuntala, love of friends and blessed of elders are deeply described by Kalidasa. In the same describe about Indian culture and human excellence.

अर्थोहि कन्या परकीय एव तामध्य संप्रेष्य परिग्रहीतुः।
ज्ञातो ममायं विशदः प्रकामं प्रत्यर्पितन्यास इवान्तरात्मा॥

In truth a daughter is another property; and having sent her to her husband, my inward soul is now intensely serene, as it is when a deposit is returned to its owner.

1.3 Religious Excellence In Abhijnanasakuntalam Of Kalidasa.

Kalidasa was great thinker of religious. He have given prime to lord Shiva in his works and pray to some other Gods.

In Abhijnanasakuntalam he have described about lord Indra, Indra was sent Matali to call Dusyanta, then Matali going there and says-

कृतः शरव्यं हरिणातवासुराः शरासनं तेषुविकृष्यतामिदम्।
प्रसादसौम्यानि सतांसुहृज्जनेपतन्ति चक्षुषि नदारूणाः शराः॥

After killing the demons lord Indra has given respect to Dusyanta, then dusyanta says to Matali in this hospitality it is the majesty of lord Indra and says-

अत्रखलुशतक्रतोरेवमहिमा स्तुत्यः।

1.4 Philosophical Excellence In Abhijnanasakuntalam Of Kalidasa.

Kalidasa also a philosophical thinker, In his works he described about the philosophical human excellence.

In the Abhijnanasakuntalam the mangalacharana or Nandi has described with vedantic philosophy.

या सृष्टिं स्रष्टुराद्यावहतिविधिहुतं या हविर्या च होत्री
ये देकालंविधतः श्रुतिविषयगुणा या स्थिता व्याप्य विश्वम्।
यामाहु सर्ववीजप्रकृतिरिति यया पारणिनः पारणवन्तः
प्रत्यक्षाभिः प्रपन्नस्तनुभिरवतुवस्ताभीरष्टाभिरीशः॥

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